

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
TIME TABLE GENERATOR SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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Abstract

The manual system of preparing time table in colleges with large number of students is very time consuming and usually ends up with various classes clashing either at same room or with same teachers having more than one class at a time. These are just due to common human errors which are very difficult to prevent in processes such as these. To overcome these problems people usually taking the previous years timetable and modifying it but still it is a tedious job to incorporate changes. To overcome all these problems we propose to make an automated system. The system will take various inputs like details of students, subjects and class rooms and teachers available, depending upon these inputs it will generate a possible time table, making optimal utilization of all resources in a way that will best suit any of constraints or college rules. List of subjects may include electives as well as core subjects. The case is similar to schools and other educational institutions. So our aim is to develop a general purpose which can efficiently generate optimal solutions.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Time table scheduling has been in human requirements since they thought of managing time effectively. It is widely used in schools, colleges and other fields of teaching and working like crash courses, coaching centers, training programs etc . In early days, time table scheduling was done manually with a single person or some group involved in task of scheduling it with their hands, which take lot of effort and time. While scheduling even the smallest constraints can take a lot of time and the case is even worse when the number of constraints or the amount of data to deal with increases. In such cases perfectly designed time table is reused for whole generation without any changes, proving to be dull in such situations. Other cases that can cause problem is when the number of employers/workers are weak, resulting in rescheduling of time table or they need to fill on empty seats urgently.

Institutions/Schools/Collages/Universities are the regular users of such time tables. They need to schedule their course to meet the need of current duration and facilities that are available to them. However, their schedule should meet the requirement of new course addition and newly enrolled students to fresh batches. This may result in rescheduling the entire time table once again for its entire batches and to be scheduled in shortest possible time before the batches course start. Another problem that occur when scheduling time table for exams. When multiple batches have exam on same day, they need to be schedules effectively taking into account all problems related to facilities that are available to conduct these exams simultaneously

1.1 Purpose

Planning timetables is one of the most complex and error-prone applications. There are still serious problems like generation of high cost time tables are occurring while scheduling and these problems are repeating frequently. Therefore there is a great requirement for an application distributing the course evenly and without collisions. Our aim here is to develop a simple, easily understandable, efficient and portable application, which could automatically generate good quality time tables with in seconds.

1.2 Benefits

TimeGene, our software allows users to generate time table for newly occurring changes in less time, with less effort and with more efficiency. It will allow users to work on and view time tables in different platforms and view different information simultaneously.

1.3 Similar Products

- aSa Timetable
- Mimsa Small School
- Timetable Mate

1.4 Timeframe Schedule

This is our proposed timeframe for our proposed TimeGene application.

Date	Event
04/10/2010	Selected time table generation as project.
05/10/2010	Started to collect various information about the topic, like different scheduling algorithms, different available sources, different education systems
21/11/2010	Analyzed different information
28/11/2010	Initially set the algorithm to be used as “Genetic algorithm”, front end as java, back end as MySQL, IDE as Eclipse
03/12/2010	Submitted SRS.
21/12/2010	Started to study the design requirements
09/01/2011	Downloaded required software including those for documentation and maintenance.
26/02/2011	Installed jdk, eclipse, mysql, kile.
20/03/2011	Started to study the various software and their functionalities
20/03/2011	Submitted our Software Design Report.
23/04/2011	Changed IDE to netbeans because of its drag and drop interface design tools and database maintaining plugins.
10/05/2011	Completed the interface design.
12/05/2011	Completed the logic.
16/06/2011	Integration and modification of interface, database and logic.
26/06/2011	Successfully completed the software
27/06/2011	Started preparing report and slides
28/06/2011	Report and slides completed

Figure 1.1: Timeframe Schedule

CHAPTER 2

Review of Literature

This chapter provides an analysis of the automated timetable literature broadly organized by algorithmic technique. It begins with a presentation of the major timetable solution generation algorithms that have persisted in the literature. A detailed examination of the academic literature is provided within the context of these fundamental solution generation algorithms. An analysis of the literature, grouped by the solution generation technique used, is then presented.

2.1 Linear Programming/Integer Programming

The Linear and Integer Programming techniques, the first applied to timetabling, were developed from the broader area of mathematical programming. Mathematical programming is applicable to the class of problems characterised by a large number of variables that intersect within boundaries imposed by a set of restraining conditions (Thompson, 1967). The word "programming" means planning in this context and is related to the type of application (Feiring, 1986). This scheme of programming was developed during World War II in connection with finding optimal strategies for conducting the war effort and used afterwards in the fields of industry, commerce and government services (Bunday, 1984).

Linear Programming (LP) is that subset of mathematical programming concerned with the efficient allocation of limited resources to known activities with the objective of meeting a desired goal such as maximising profits or minimising costs (Feiring,

1986). Integer Programming (IP) deals with the solution of mathematical programming problems in which some or all of the variables can assume non-negative integer values only. Although LP methods are very valuable in formulating and solving problems related to the efficient use of limited resources they are not restricted to only these problems (Bunday, 1984). Linear programming problems are generally acknowledged to be efficiently solved by just three methods, namely the graphical method, the simplex method, and the transportation method (see eg, Palmers and Innes, 1976; Makower and Williamson, 1985).

The construction of a linear programming model involves three successive problem-solving steps. The first step identifies the unknown or independent decision variables. Step two requires the identification of the constraints and the formulation of these constraints as linear equations. Finally, in step three, the objective function is identified and written as a linear function of the decision variables.

2.2 Evolutionary and Genetic Algorithms

Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) are a class of direct, probabilistic search and optimisation algorithms gleaned from the model of organic evolution. A Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a type of EA and is regarded as being the most widely known EA in recent times.

A GA differs from other search techniques in the following ways:

- GAs optimise the trade-off between exploring new points in the search space and exploiting the information discovered thus far.
- GAs have the property of implicit parallelism. Implicit parallelism means that the GAs effect is equivalent to an extensive search of hyper planes of the given space, without directly testing all hyper plane values . Each schema denotes a hyper plane.

- GAs are randomised algorithms, in that they use operators whose results are governed by probability. The results for such operations are based on the value of a random number . This means GAs use probabilistic transition rules, not deterministic rules.
- GAs operate on several solutions simultaneously, gathering information from current search points to a direct subsequent search. Their ability to maintain multiple solutions concurrently makes them less susceptible to the convergence problem of local maxima and noise .
- GAs work with a coding of the parameter set, not the parameters themselves.
- GAs search from a population of points, not a single point .
- GAs use payoff (objective function) information, not derivatives or other auxiliary knowledge .

It is demonstrated that the literature is currently converging on the use of constraint based solution algorithms and implementations. It is also noted that the next most commonly reported implementation involves the use of hybrid algorithms.

CHAPTER 3

TimeGene

In this chapter we are presenting various details of our final product. Since the project is currently in a developing stage so most of the details are yet to be verified. So below we present the basic details.

3.1 Product Name

TimeGene, an abbreviation for TIME table GENERator is a simple graphical user interface that will allow users to easily generate the required time table for their newly enrolled batches; developed by ABSR (Anoop, Benson, Sarath, Rishla) group.

3.2 Product Description

TimeGene is a general purpose tool for generating different types of tables. It can give good outputs for most of the systems like school system, our university systems, and French university systems and so on.

Some of the most common constraints to deal with are listed below. Some of these are soft constraints meaning they only increase the cost. Some are hard which cannot be violated.

Hard Constraints

- No teacher or student must be assigned to more than one class.

- There should be required number of periods for each course.
- Each course must have required consecutive periods. For example lab is assigned to 3 or 4 consecutive hours.

Soft Constraints

- Courses must be evenly distributed
- Same teacher must not have consecutive periods unless specified.

3.3 Product Features

Some of the most important features offered by our software are

- Simple wizard type user interface
- Login authentication with MySQL login details
- Message dialogs for user assistance.
- Mouse or/and keyboard for inputs, keyboard shortcuts are available.
- Separate database maintaining basic informations, subjects, teachers, batches and their associations and other details
- Database for holding generated timetable and for storing required timetables.
- Features for assigning priorities for subjects.
- Features for editing generated table, saving edited tables and opening saved tables
- High portability, works on almost all systems available.
- Highly efficient, needs only few minutes to complete whole procedure

CHAPTER 4

Requirement Analysis

This chapter gives minimum requirement your system should have in order to make this software work. This software works fine in any operating system in which the developer tools or the user tools can be installed. Since we had limited resources we could only test in Windows 7, Windows XP, Ubuntu 11.04, Ubuntu 10.10. So usually the requirement specification will be same as that of the operating system. So we are providing a standard specification.

4.1 System Configuration

- 1 GHz x86 processor
- 1GB of system memory (RAM)
- 15GB of hard-drive space
- Monitor to display output
- Keyboard/Mouse for data input

4.2 Developer tools

Front end : Netbeans with Sun's/Oracle Java Development Kit

Back end : MySQL essentials(server), MySQL JDBC connector

4.3 User tools

Sun's/Oracle Java Run Time Environment

MySQL essentials(server), MySQL JDBC connector

4.4 Tools for Documentation

- Kile 2.1(L^AT_EX)
- Microsoft Visio 2010
- Ubuntu Screenshot
- OpenOffice.org Presentation
- OpenOffice.org Word Processor
- Gimp/Photoshop CS4

CHAPTER 5

Overview

This chapter gives an overview of the system in the use case diagram, overview of the activities in the work break down diagram, overview of the working of activities in data flow diagram, and overview of the database in ER diagram

5.1 Use case diagram

As shown in the figure the Database Entry Operator(DEO) is responsible of the system. He should be aware of various courses and subjects available in the college, he should also know the various rules and regulations of the institution. His job is as follows

- Collect teachers' information
- Collect students' information
- Input these information to the system
- Provide the output to others
- Make necessary modifications
- Maintain the database for future works

The DEO must have some basic knowledge about computers. He or she must have the skill to properly address the priorities. Time Gene will take care of the rest. It will provide teachers view for teachers and subject view for students.

Figure 5.1: Use case Diagram

Figure 5.2: Work Breakdown Structure

5.2 Work Breakdown Structure

Above is a activity based work breakdown structure. The diagram shows how we divided the whole process into simpler ones. Each of the process is carried out by various group members. Most of the steps are repeated again and again in the life cycle of the project.

5.3 Data flow diagram

The data flow through database is described in following diagram. Each process represent the working of user with the interface and followed by its associated operation performed in the database. Here open square represents the operation that is performed in databases.

Figure 5.3: Data flow Diagram

Figure 5.4: ER Diagram

5.4 ER diagram

The database schema is represented by the ER Diagram. Here each box represent a table. The table name is given at the top and the fields are given at the bottom. The bold italics fields are the primary keys used, along with field name its data type and length are given.

- **info** table stores general information such as college name, academic year, working hours and days and stores information in its associated fields in database.

- **batches** table stores information of the batches such as batch id and name.
- **teachers** table stores information of teachers such as teacher id and name.
- **subjects** table stores information of subjects such as subject id, name, working hours and the number of teachers needed.
- **sub_tea** table stores association of subjects and teachers. Here the **subid** is the foreign key associated with the **id** of the teachers table and the **batid** refers the **id** of the batches table.
- **bat_sub** table stores association of batches and subjects. Here the **batid** is the foreign key associated with the **id** of the batches table and the **subid** refers the **id** of the subjects table.
- **tim_tab** stores the generated time table and it is associated with all other tables.

CHAPTER 6

Implementation

This application has been developed using Java as front end tool and MySQL Server as its back end tool. The application has been coded to be platform independent running on Java Virtual Machine.

Netbeans IDE has been chosen as its development environment because of the following features

- Designing interface for the application has been simplified by its drag and drop GUI pallet.
- Debugging can be easily done using the Logger class.
- Easy database access with NetBeans database plugin.
- Simplified automated editor error detection.
- Automatic code generation.
- Automatic dcumentation.
- Simplified class factory method lookups.
- Easy to create jar files using build option.
- Profiling option.
- Project can be run on debugging mode which provides current state of the variables with the help of break points.
- NetBeans IDE has wide help and support on the web.

While coding TimeGene application several constraints related to its computation has been taken into account.

Timetable generating problem provides us with various alternatives in the design of the algorithm, interface and the database. Among the various designs what we have implemented is detailed below

6.1 Interface Implementation

There are ten classes each contains a JFrame which is associated with an interface. The association are as follows

- Main.class for login interface
- TimeGene.class for basic information interface
- Subjects.class for subject interface
- Teachers.class for teachers interface
- Batches.class for batches interface
- SubTea.class for Subject Teacher interface
- BatTea.class for Batch Teacher interface
- SelBat.class for Batches Selection and Priority interface
- ShowTable.class for Timetable Output interface
- SelectTable.class for open and save interface

6.1.1 Login Interface

Enter the MySQL login name and password as a primary information

6.1.2 Basic Information Interface

Enter basic information related to collage name, academic year, select working hours from drop down list and select check boxes for working days. To open saved table click on Open Table. To know more on TimeGene click About.

6.1.3 Subject Interface

Enter the Subject ID and Subject Name, enter continuous working hours per week, enter the number of teachers needed in subject and click Save. To edit select the Subject ID and click Save. To remove select the Subject ID and click Remove.

6.1.4 Teacher Interface

Enter the Teacher ID and Teacher Name and click Save. To edit select the Teacher ID and click Save. To remove select the Teacher ID and click Remove.

6.1.5 Batch Interface

Enter the Batch ID and Batch Name and click Save. To edit select the Batch ID and click Save. To remove select the Batch ID and click Remove.

6.1.6 Subject-Teacher Interface

Select the Subject ID and their respective Teacher ID. Click the double headed symbol to add or remove from Selected Teachers list.

6.1.7 Batch-Subject Interface

Select the Batch ID and their respective Subject ID. Click the double headed symbol to add or remove from the Selected Subjects list.

6.1.8 Batch Selection Interface

Select the Batches to be scheduled. Click the double headed symbol to add or remove from the Selected Batches list and if necessary set or remove subjects priority for the selected batch. The priority is set by selecting subject, day, hour from the drop down list.

6.1.9 Timetable Output Interface

Select Batch tab to view associated batch time table. Select teachers view or subjects view to display time table in teacher or subject respectively. To edit generated list select the period and edit using keyboard. To save generated time table click Save.

6.1.10 Save Table Interface

Enter filename to be saved to the database and select save. To replace an existing file or delete a file, use delete and then save the new timetable to the database. To avoid changes click cancel.

6.1.11 Open Table Interface

Select the filename and click the Open Table option. To delete an existing file, select the file and click delete. To go back press cancel.

6.2 Algorithm Implementation

TimeTable generation is an NP-Complete problem; specifically speaking NP-Hard. So it lacks a proper time bound for execution i.e. problems like these often can have many different outputs. So we assign cost to each output which gives the measure of deviation of the output from the desired one. So our aim is to get the output with minimum cost if there is one.

Genetic algorithm can give best results but the time needed for it to compute cannot be determined so we have developed an alternative approach which can be applied to solve most of the NP-Complete problems.

- First determine the various constraints which the output must satisfy.
- We then categorize them as soft and hard constraints.
- Third step is to make a procedure which can generate an output for most of the possible inputs.
- The final step is to reduce the cost.

The current working scenarios these can be explained as follows

The first two steps are explained earlier. The procedure mentioned in the third step here is the `gene()` function in the `selbat` class. What this function does is to assign priorities to teacher, subject and position. So that if we arrange timetable according to this priority there is a greater probability to end up in the output which satisfies all the hard constraints.

First and foremost priority is that of teachers. Subject priority and position priority depends on teacher priority, also teacher is the most important resource in the time table.

The priority of teacher increases if the number of periods he handled increases, also if the number of batches he is present increases and decreases if an alternative teacher is available.

Subject priority is also similar to that of teacher priority. It must also increase with the continuous hours needed. So in the algorithm we have considered subject which have different consecutive periods need as different subjects.

Position has priority if it correctly fits and the adjacent portions are not that of the same subject.

Finally we need to manually assign priority and optimize the table to reduce cost.

The main logic of our algorithm resides in the `selbat` class. The `gene` function in the class reads the various data needed for generation of timetable for current batches from the database creates the table in an **ArrayList** and copies it back to the database.

6.3 Database Implementation

In order to incorporate portability we use MySQL as our backend. It provides many features such as different engines and high end sql commands to create and manipulate database. It also provides tools called MySQL dump to backup database.

In our project as mentioned in the ER diagram, we use a single database called `time_gene` which contains the above mentioned tables. Engine for table other than `info` and `tim_tab` are made InnoDB for foreign key annotation, whereas `info` and `tim_tab` are made MyISAM for easy editing and backup.

Primary keys are properly assigned for each table except the `info` as to avoid duplicate entries which may later create problems. Eventhough we designed GUI so as to avoid such conditions, still we don't recommend to accessing the database directly. Our algorithm assumes that the database entries are correct so any changes may cause problem.

The software when installed first checks if such a database is available, if not found it automatically creates the necessary tables.

The default engine for window is InnoDB and that for linux is MyISAM these are properly addressed in our database. So the user need not worry anything about database creation.

We added a feature to save time table from generated table (`tim_tab`). It simply copies the data in `tim_tab` to a table with starting name saved.

Besides this, a user can backup other tables or the whole database using `mysqldump` command but its procedure differs on different operating systems. Later this backup can be restored.

CHAPTER 7

Testing

Testing is an important phase in software lifecycle. Testing improves reliability and robustness of the application. The basic operations to be tested are

- There should be at least one working day and one working hour
- Different inputs must be checked for its range. For example no of hours in morning or evening should be between 0-5, total number of periods for a course must be between 0-70, code for course must be 0-8 character long.
- User should not be given permission to edit or modify subjects, teachers or batches without releasing its associations
- Opening and saving of databases should show exceptions if they occur (same file should not be used while saving)
- Before generating table it should be checked if all subjects are assigned at least one teacher, no of periods available($((\text{morning hours} + \text{evening hours}) * \text{no of days})$) must be equal to no of periods assigned.
- If any problem occurs during generation (due to constraints) it must be properly displayed.

Test Approach

The system is to be tested at various stages of the project development:

Each user interface is tested individually for its function. Interfaces meant for data input are tested by entering data in the data tables through each interface. Similarly each data base operation is tested through interfaces.

All the user interfaces are joined in the desired sequence and their back end coding is tested for the desired result. Like previous window close as the next desired window opens and each button performs its desired task etc.

Every class in the java code is tested individually with the help of test cases.

Whole of the algorithm is tested with sample run of data to generate an optimal time table for the provided database.

Test Planning

Most of the testing requires checking connectivity of the user interfaces with the database, so a properly designed database is required for testing.

Design interfaces and connect each of them to the database and test them for proper output as is it is in the database.

Inter connect all the user interfaces in the desired sequence. Check if each of the buttons result in the desired result.

Develop the java classes for data retrieval. Test each of them according to test cases.

Develop java code for timetable generation. Test the coding with a small database by generating a time table.

7.1 Functional Test Criteria

The objective of these test is to ensure that each element of the application meets the functional requirement of the user.

- Requirements Catalogue

- Other functional documents produced during the course of the project i.e. resolution to issues/change requests/feedback.
- Validation Testing - which is intensive testing of the new Front end fields and screens. Windows GUI Standards; valid, invalid and limit data input; screen look and appearance, and overall consistency with the rest of the application.
- Functional testing - these are low-level tests which aim to test the individual processes and data flows.

7.2 Integration Testing

This test proves that all areas of the system interface with each other correctly and that there are no gaps in the data flow. Final Integration Test proves that system works as integrated unit when all the fixes are complete.

7.3 User Acceptance Test

This test, which is planned and executed by the User Representative(s), ensures that the system operates in the manner expected, and any supporting material such as procedures, forms etc. are accurate and suitable for the purpose intended. It is high level testing, ensuring that there are no gaps in functionality.

7.4 System Test Criteria

Entrance Criteria

- All developed code must be unit tested. Unit and Link Testing must be completed and signed off by development team.

- All human resources must be assigned and in place.
- All test hardware and environments must be in place, and free for System test use.

Exit Criteria

- All High Priority errors from System Test must be fixed and tested

7.5 Test cases and Test results

Outlined below are the main test types that are performed for this release. All test entries on wrong input has been tested to verify code stability and correctness. The test cases presented here are based on criterias presented above to validate its test implementation. Each test case table list the detailed test case results for each interface and its user inputs that can be assigned by the user to check the correctness of its implementation.

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
login	Main	Enter mysql login	*Enter Username *Enter Password *Click Ok *Click Cancel	*Access denied	*If Ok go to TimeGene *If Cancel then exit

Figure 7.1: Login

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
basicInfo	TimeGene	Enter basic information	*Enter Collage name *Enter academic year *Select Working Days and Hours *Click Open Table *Click Next	*At least one working day should be selected *At least one working hour should be selected	*Saves information to database *If Open Table then show saved time table *If next then show Subject interface

Figure 7.2: TimeGene

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
SavedInfo	Open Table	Select/show Saved Time Table	*Click Open *Click Cancel *Click Delete	*Table Saved Does not Exist	*If Open then open selected table saved and go to TimeGene interface *If Cancel return to TimeGene interface *If Delete then delete selected saved time table

Figure 7.3: Open Table

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
SubInfo	Subjects	Enter Subject Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Enter Subject ID * Enter Subject Name * Select Periods per week * Enter Number of teachers for the subject * Select Subject ID from Subject list * Click Save * Click Remove * Click Back *Click Next 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Data too long for column id * Please input positive numbers for hour *Total periods should be less 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Save then save the result to database and show saved Subject ID in Subjects list * If Remove then removes the Teachers details from list and database * If Back then go to TimeGene interface *If Next then go to Teachers interface

Figure 7.4: Subject

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
TeaInfo	Teachers	Enter Teachers Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Enter Teacher ID * Enter Teacher Name * Select Teacher ID from Teachers list * Click Save * Click Remove * Click Back *Click Next 	* Data too long for column id	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Save then save the result to database and show saved Teachers ID in Teachers list * If Remove then removes the Teacher details from list and database * If Back then go to Subjects interface *If next then go to Batches Interface

Figure 7.5: Teacher

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
BatInfo	Batches	Enter Batch Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Enter Batch ID * Enter Batch Name * Select Batch ID from Batch list * Click Save * Click Remove * Click Back *Click Next 	* Data too long for column id	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Save then save the result to database and show saved Batch ID in Batches list * If Remove then removes the Batch details from list and database * If Back then go to Teacher interface * If next then go to Subject-Teacher interface

Figure 7.6: Batch

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
SubTeaInfo	Subjects Teachers	Enter Subject Teacher Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Select Subject ID * Select Teacher ID * Click Back Arrow * Click Front Arrow * Click Next * Click Back 	* Select Teacher From List	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Front Arrow then Add to Subject Teacher List * If Back Arrow then Remove from Subjects Teachers List * If Back then go to Batches Interface * If Next then go to Next then go to Batches Teachers Interface

Figure 7.7: Subject-Teacher

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
BatTeaInfo	Batches Subject	Enter Batches Subject Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Select Batch ID * Select Subject ID * Click Back Arrow * Click Front Arrow * Click Next * Click Back 	* Select Subject From List	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Front Arrow then Add to Batch Subject List * If Back Arrow then Remove from Batches Subjects List * If Back then go to Subject Teacher Interface * If Next then go to Next then go to Select Batches Interface

Figure 7.8: Batch-Subject

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
SelBatInfo	Select Batches	Select Batches to view Time Table	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Select Batch ID * Click Back Arrow * Click Front Arrow * Click Next * Click Back 	* Select Batch from List	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If Front Arrow then Add to Batches List * If Back Arrow then Remove from Batches List * If Back then go to Batches Subjects Teacher Interface * If Next then go to Next then go to Table View Interface

Figure 7.9: Batch Select

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
TabViewInfo	Table View	Show Time Table information	*Select Batch View tab *Select Teachers View *Select Subject View *Select Save *Select Back	*Nil	*If Batch tab then show batch table * If Teacher view then show teachers timetable * If Subject view then show subjects timetable *If Save then show Save Interface *If back then go to Select Batch

Figure 7.10: Table View

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION	STEPS	EXPECTED ERROR	EXPECTED RESULT
SaveInfo	Save	Save new time table to database	*Enter Save As name * Click Save *Click Delete *Click Cancel	*Nil	*If Save then save table to database and go to TimeGene interface *If Cancel return to Table View Interface *If Delete then delete selected saved time table

Figure 7.11: Save

CHAPTER 8

Conclusion and Future Works

8.1 Conclusion

TimeGene application will simplify the process of time table generation smoothly which may otherwise needed to done using spread sheet manually possibly leading to constraints problem that are difficult to determine when time table is generated manually.

8.2 Future works

TimeGene future works may include:

1. Student Room Scheduling

This will allow room scheduling for students in particular batches where there are multiple sections with strong strength.

2. Exam Time Table Generation

This will allow teachers/users to develop time table smoothly when multiple batches is required to hold exams .

3. Exam Room Scheduling This will allow users to schedule rooms for students effectively.

4. Time Constrain Problem

Some institute have large campus where travelling time is needed to be considered.

5. Generating different Choices of Time Table.

By exchanging weeks or periods using Genetic Algorithm of generated timetable various choice for time table can be provided.

6. User Period Information

System can be made in such a way that it can generate time table keeping certain periods as supplied by the users.

CHAPTER 9

Appendix

9.1 Instalation Manual

- Install jre
- Install mysql-essentials
- On **Windows** double click on TimeGene.jar or TimeGene.bat
- On **Linux** run in terminal TimeGene.sh or type in terminal "sh path/TimeGene.sh" or "bash path/TimeGene.sh"
- To run in shell/Command prompt type java -jar path/TimeGene.jar
- login with your mysql login username and password
- Enter necessary informations (described in user interface scenarios)
- Get the desired time table as output

9.2 User interface Scenarios

User interface Scenarios gives a brief preview of user interface.

Figure 9.1: Login Prompt

Figure 9.2: Basic Information

Subjects' Information

Subjects

Select

- it301
- it302
- it303
- it304
- it305
- it306
- it307
- it308
- it501
- it502
- it503
- it504
- it505
- it506
- it507
- it508
- it701
- it702
- it703
- it704
- it705
- it706
- it707
- it708

Code

Name

Hours per week	Enter no. of teachers needed
1 x <input type="text" value="0"/>	<input type="text" value="1"/>
2 x <input type="text" value="0"/>	
3 x <input type="text" value="0"/>	
4 x <input type="text" value="0"/>	
5 x <input type="text" value="0"/>	

Figure 9.3: Subjects' Information

Teachers' Information

Teachers

Select

- askm
- hp
- js
- mat
- mech
- r
- spr
- ss
- sv
- vkk
- vs
- wvav

Id

Name

Remove Save

<Back Next>

Figure 9.4: Teachers' Information

Figure 9.5: Batches' Information

Figure 9.6: Subject Teacher Association

Figure 9.7: Batch Subject Association

Figure 9.8: Current Batches and Priorities

The screenshot shows a window titled "Time Table" for "Govt.Enng College,SKP 2011". It has tabs for "s3", "s5", and "s7", with "s3" selected. There are radio buttons for "Subjects View" (selected) and "Teachers View". The table below shows the subject assignments for each day and hour.

DAY	Hour1	Hour2	Hour3	Hour4	Hour5	Hour6
MON	it307	it307	it307	it306	it304	it305
TUE	it308	it308	it308	it306	it305	it302
WED	it306	it303	it304	it303	it302	it301
THU	it306	it304	it305	it303	it302	it301
FRI	it303	it304	it305	it303	it301	it301

At the bottom of the window are "<Back" and "Save" buttons.

Figure 9.9: Generated Time Table

Figure 9.10: Save Time Table after editing

Figure 9.11: Open saved Time Table

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